

DPU Dr. D. Y. Patil
B-School

(Program Approved by AICTE, Ministry of Education, Govt. of India)

Presents

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

of International Conference on

**Fostering Resilient Business
Ecosystems and Economic
Growth: Towards the Next Normal**

(April 27 to 29, 2022)

Editors

Dr. Amol Gawande

Dr. Atul Kumar

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School

Tathawade, Mumbai Bangalore Highway

Pune 411033, Maharashtra, India

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INFLUENCER MARKETING ON SOCIAL MEDIA FOR HOME GROWN INDIAN BRANDS

Prof. (Dr.) Atul Kumar

Research Guide Savitribai Phule Pune
University (SPPU), Pune,
atulk.singh@yahoo.co.in, 9604136798

Prof. Neha Saxena

Research Scholar Savitribai Phule Pune
University (SPPU), Pune,
neha.saxenain@gmail.com, 9527368556

Abstract:

In India, the mobile phone revolution has changed several aspects of life, especially the business of advertising and marketing. Influencer marketing on social media using endorsements and product mentions from influencers that was earlier confined to celebrities and bloggers has grown bigger. Brands are re-imagining their businesses of marketing their products/services by building communities and roping in normal people as content creators. Instagram, YouTube and Facebook are becoming an instant hit allowing people to share reels, pictures/videos instantly. Influencers are people with a huge follower base on some or all of the social media platforms and brands are increasingly roping in these influencers to create a pull in the market for their products/services. These thought leaders create content to influence the idea of people online.

3.1 Purpose:

The primary purpose of the research is to understand how the use of technology and innovative online content by influencers develop a level of trust between the brand and the consumer and eventually leads to purchase. Studies have shown that online shopping in India has accelerated by 2-3 years in a matter of weeks after the first lockdown began in 2020. Digitally influenced purchases increased by up to 25% amongst urban consumers, in just three months. Brands have been collaborating with influencers to promote their products, services, events and more like never before since the onset of the pandemic.

With “Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan” picking up in India and with people consuming lot of online content, the brands started assigning their budgets to digital instead of TV, print, etc. Also, the kind of relatable content the influencers were generating during the

pandemic in English, Hindi and vernacular languages gave a further boost to influencer marketing.

3.2 Methodology:

This study is a Descriptive study. Some amount of primary data was collected from consumers who have purchased online after getting influenced by the content created by influencers. However, the majority of secondary data was collected from different sources like company websites, blogs, social media data, research reports, research papers, books, journals and magazines.

3.3 Major findings:

- a) The India Influencer Marketing Report 2021 estimates that the influencer marketing industry in India is currently worth Rs. 900 crores, and that is only set to grow further.
- b) The report estimates that the industry is poised to grow at a CAGR of 25% for the next decade reaching a size of Rs. 2,200 crores in 2025.
- c) Influencer marketing was an integral part of the marketing mix before pandemic too, but it became more relevant during the covid time.
- d) Research by Exchange4Media shows that over 80% of the consumers surveyed have purchased something via an influencer recommendation.
- e) The return on investment (ROI) for influencer marketing campaigns is 11 times more than traditional ads.
- f) The primary platform the influencers focus is Instagram because of its focus on short-format video content such as Reels and Stories. It gives the best outcome for brands and influencers in terms of sales and ROI.
- g) ROI is measured in terms of post views, likes, website/link visits, contest entries and use of coupon codes etc. However, it differs from campaign to campaign.

3.4 Implications of the research:

a) Small budget, big influence:

Brands could begin with Influencer marketing starting from as low as a couple of thousands. Influencers with smaller fan bases also generate worthy revenue with engaged audiences.

b) Builds validity and trust:

Influencers develop a sense of trust among their followers basis of which they make their buying decisions.

c) Intimacy in approach:

The content is more relatable and personalized specially in regional languages which has gained good popularity.

d) Helps in building brand awareness:

This kind of marketing generates good brand awareness and has high top of the mind recall value.

e) Tracking influencer success:

Influencer campaigns give immediate results because they can be tracked for ongoing updates and the revenue gathered via a URL.

1. Keywords:

Home grown brands, Influencer marketing, Social media

2. Introduction:

5.1 Background:

While more than 400 million Indians already had access to social media before the pandemic, they started spending more time on social media during the lockdown and from an average 150 mins per day, they started spending about 280 mins per day on the platforms. This behavioural change led to the rise of social media influencers. Over the past two years, influencer marketing has really caught up and is proving to be a real game changer.

5.2 Objectives of the Study:

- a) To understand the emerging trends in Influencer marketing domain adopted by home grown brands
- b) To identify how and why influencer marketing is becoming an integral part of marketing budgets for home grown brands
- c) To determine how “changed social media behaviour” of consumers during lockdown in 2020 due to pandemic made way to the rise of social media influencers
- d) To analyse the various platforms used by home grown brands to promote their products and build a strong connect with consumers through influencer marketing

3. Literature Review:

With excessive increase in the number of people accessing the social media platforms and spending more time on it specially during the lockdown, the data showed that from an average 150 mins per day, people started spending about 280 mins per day on the social media platforms. This behavioural change led to the rise of social media influencers. Over the past two years, influencer marketing has caught up tremendously well giving rise to an array of influencers. Brands are leveraging from this concept in turn giving instant projects/way of earning to general people with certain number of followers on certain social media platforms.

Below are some broad categories of influencers who are popular on social media platforms specially Instagram:

Nano influencers:

10,000 followers or less. Influencers with the highest percentage of engagement because of their small and a more close-knit community of followers. They also have more flexibility in working on campaigns, which works well for brands. They do stories, statistic posts and reels

Micro influencers:

(10,000 to 50,000 followers). These influencers charge for reels and posts and also do some stories

Mid influencers:

(50,000 to 1,00,000 followers). These influencers work with brands and charge for reels, posts and some stories. They prefer to work on package basis

Macro influencers:

(1,00,000 – 1 million followers). These influencers work on package deals with few reels, posts and complimentary stories

Mega influencers:

(1million + followers). These are celebrity influencers who charge heavy for every content they post

Initially, small influencers begin with barter deals instead of cash payouts. Once they gain enough traction and have greater follower count, they also claim for travel and stay.

The primary platform the influencers focus is Instagram because of its focus on short-format video content such as Reels and Stories. It gives the best outcome for brands and influencers in terms of sales and ROI that can be measured in terms of post views, likes, website/link visits, contest entries and use of coupon codes etc. However, it differs from campaign to campaign.

4. Research Methods:

The method used to collect data for this Descriptive study is a mix of primary and secondary research. However, due to time constraint some amount of primary data was collected from consumers who have purchased online, are aware about influencer marketing concept and have bought something online after getting influenced by the influencers. The secondary data was collected from different sources like company websites, industry magazines, research reports, research papers, books and journals.

5. Results and Discussions:

8.1 Results:

Influencer marketing is comparatively a new concept for home grown brands in India. However, it has gained enough popularity and picked up momentum after a massive increase in the social media consumption in our country. There are different categories of influencers depending on the number of followers they have on social media.

- a) The companies have started putting in major chunk of their marketing budgets into digital marketing due to better reach and clear results without any waste.
- b) Influencer marketing reinforces a brand's reputation and fosters credibility. Also, partnering with influencers helps to gain the trust of their audience.
- c) Influencer marketing is the perfect tool to grow an army of loyal brand advocates and earning more revenue.
- d) Successful influencer marketing involves identifying the right type of influencer who will offer curated advice, stories, and suggestions to create engagement with the audience.
- e) Initially, small influencers begin with barter deals instead of cash payouts. Once they gain enough traction and have greater follower count, they also claim for travel and stay.
- f) The primary platform the influencers focus is Instagram because of its focus on short-format video content such as Reels and Stories. It gives the best outcome for brands and influencers in terms of sales and ROI.

8.2 Significance of the research:

The research is very significant for companies/ brands which are home grown and clearly made in India with appeal to Indian and overseas audience. These companies have comparatively lower budgets and they look for ROI in every penny they spend. It will be significant for:

- Customers:**
Prospective customers look up to influencers to make their purchase decisions. With variety and tough competition between brands in the market, it is equally beneficial in retaining the existing customers.
- Influencers:**
The online thought leaders whose performance is constantly monitored and evaluated as companies enter into performance-based influencer marketing models. Influencers are expected to deliver concrete results like no. of sales or clicks. There is a huge variation in the earnings of influencers and may vary as per their follower base, popularity, engagement rate, brand partnerships, location and so on.
- Industry:**
Influencer marketing as industry is massive yet comparatively less organized. With influencer marketing getting bigger, eventually there will be a need for some regulations and guidelines to be officially planned and implemented by governing bodies like ASCI. Disparity in influencer rates and pay out patterns by brands is also something that needs to be seen and studied.
- Brands:**
There is difficulty in assessing digital engagement and actual returns for brands. They seek out long term partnerships with a correct mix of influencers, platforms and models that can give them better returns. In an attempt to make their products more accessible and relatable, the brands are eyeing regional influencers for collaborations.
- Public in general:**
Since, anyone and everyone with certain traits and followers can jump on the bandwagon and become an influencer, it is very important for general public to be aware about the plethora of opportunities that this industry offers.

6. Conclusion:

While the future seems promising with the digital platform emerging and constantly growing as the new marketplace, there are few ifs and buts that needs to be plugged in.

- a) The influencers market in itself is not very well organized and streamlined.
- b) There is no formal structure defined as to what kind of influencer will be more beneficial for what kind of products/services.
- c) There is limited research done on this industry with no documented laws or rules that could set the influencer categories and the price ranges they work in.
- d) With less investment and limited capital, the companies are shifting focus to online media for all their marketing needs. Online medium has emerged as one of the strongest mediums in terms of managing all advertising and marketing needs of a brand without any waste and better measurement of results.
- e) Influencers have a certain life in the market. A proper tracking has to be done in terms of their followership and immediate reach. The success of the campaign also depends on the digital stability of an influencer.

7. References:

1. Ashish Kumar (GurukulaKangriVishwavidyalaya) Ram Bezawada (University at Buffalo, The State University of New York) P.K. Kannan (University of Maryland, College Park) (2015) From Social to Sale: The Effects of Firm Generated Content in social media on Customer Behavior, *Journal of Marketing* 80(1), DOI:10.1509/jm.14.0249
2. Anjali Chopra, VrushaliAvhad and SonaliJaju (June 2020), Influencer Marketing: An Exploratory Study to Identify Antecedents of Consumer Behavior of Millennial, DOI:10.1177/2278533720923486
3. Ghosal, I., Prasad, P., Behera, M. P., & Kumar, A. (2021). Depicting the Prototype Change in Rural Consumer Behaviour: An Empirical Survey on Online Purchase Intention. *Paradigm*, 25(2), 161-180. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/09718907211029030>
4. YasameenThaer (Kadir Has University), (May 2019), The impact of trust on social media's influencers and the effect of influencer's discount codes on the consumer purchase involvement, Thesis for: Masters of Business Administration
5. Marijke De Veirman (Artevelde University College), LiselotHudders (Ghent University), Michelle R. Nelson, (December 2019), What Is Influencer Marketing and How Does It Target Children - A Review and Direction for Future Research, *Frontiers in Psychology*, DOI:10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02685
6. Kumar, A., Gawande, A., & Brar, V. (2020). Marketing Tactics in Times of Covid-19. *Vidyabharati International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(1), 263-266. Wikipedia
7. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342181914_Influencer_Marketing_An_Exploratory_Study_to_Identify_Antecedents_of_Consumer_Behavior_of_Millennial
8. Outlook Business magazine (November, 2021 issue) – special issue on India’s Top Influencers Social media influencers

ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

“Next Normal” is the latest buzzword two years after the Covid -19 pandemic hit all the sections of society and the economy. With the havoc now seemingly showing the downturn, it's the “Next to Normal” that will define 2022 and the subsequent years. Covid-19 has changed the world, society, and business function. With the Next Normal, the future demands resilience. Resilience is the CEO agenda of every company and across all industries. Businesses are reconsidering their approaching order to make it more resilient. Re-evaluating one's supply base, geographical footprint, moving with speed to digitize the operations end to end, encouraging flexibility to create new value for the customers, and increasing competitive advantage are certain considerations that need to be undertaken to build a resilient ecosystem for economic growth in the Next Normal. The 'Next Normal' also calls for innovative ways to re-engage an organization's human resources and marketing techniques. Other measures such as financial assistance, devising a favorable environment for the growth of startups, and regional collaboration among ecosystem developers can play an essential role in transforming the way businesses work are the other factors business leaders should consider as they prepare for “The Next Normal.” There is a need for in-depth scientific reflection regarding the methods and instruments for economic development in theoretical and practical terms. In this background, the prime goal of this Conference is to be a platform for discussing scientific achievements and evaluate the current state of research development on the role of institutional, financial, and technological innovation in fostering a resilient business ecosystem and economic growth.

ABOUT US

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School runs AICTE approved PGDM program. It has been ranked 1st Emerging B-School among top institutes of west India by Times of India. It has also been conferred the ET Now Business School of the Year award. The two-year full-time PGDM program offered by Dr. D.Y. Patil B-School is designed to empower students to become successful business professionals in the challenging global scenario. The Institute is continually evolving to meet its goals in an ever-changing business environment. It has been playing an important role in professionalizing Indian management through its programs. Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School aims to create value-driven leaders, global managers and entrepreneurs with strong conceptual foundations and analytical approach to help them be the best in whichever field they choose. The aim is to innovatively address the needs of a modern India and connecting aspirations and realities to attain benchmarks that are respected internationally.

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School

Sr. No. 87-88, Bengaluru-Mumbai Express Bypass,
Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India

Contact No. : 8007989201

Email : info.bschool@dpu.edu.in

Website : www.bschool.dpu.edu.in